

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MARKET ORIENTATION AND SERVICE QUALITY: WITH
REFERENCE TO INDIAN BANKS IN RAJASTHAN**

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Abstract:

Banking has grown at an incredible pace all across India, especially in the metropolitan cities. However, customer expectation from the service provider and their behavior patterns are not permanently fixed, and certainly not sacred, even though some habits tenaciously resist change. Market Orientation, Service quality and customer satisfaction are very vital concepts that banks must understand in order to remain competitive in business and hence grow. This paper highlights the relationship of market orientation and service quality. The reliability of the developed questionnaire was tested by deploying the statistical test 'Cronbach's alpha' to the responses received. Correlation analysis is conducted for finding out the relationship between market orientation and service quality. It is concluded that there is a significant and positive relation between Market orientation and service quality. Market orientation practice like intelligence generation, intelligence dissemination and responsiveness influence service quality provided to customers. In order to improve performance and quality of services, banks have to focus on market orientation.

Key words: Service quality, Market orientation, and Banks

1. Introduction

With fast changing environment everything is changing. It may be technology, education, market, financial services etc. Most of the companies have shifted their focus from production oriented to market or customer oriented and also, they are continuously working for improvement in service quality. Market Orientation and Service quality plays a very important role in enhancing the organizational performance. When we talk about service sector, banks are very important. Banks helps in capital formation and building a strong economic environment for smooth functioning of various financial activities.

The concept of marketing is to achieve organisational goals after determining the needs and wants of the markets to satisfy their customers. So, the basic factors are target market, customer need, integrated marketing and profitability. Gradually, marketing concept has become more comprehensive in determining and fulfilling customer expectations.

The main motto of marketing is to provide comfort and efficiency to customers beyond the level of their expectations. Business started looking at a situation from the customer's perspective and their focus shifted to the wants of customers.

Jaworski and Kohli proposed three dimensions of market orientation which are intelligence generation, intelligence dissemination and market responsiveness. Jaworski and Kohli differ from Narver and Slater with regard to the use of cultural dimensions. Nevertheless, the components of market orientation are apparently similar. They argue that the organisational dimensions are crucial. They also point out that the market orientation is concerned not only with the present but also future needs of customers. The MARKOR scale is a 20-item, 5-point Likert Scale.

The three components of MARKOR scale are explained as follows:

- (a) **Intelligence Generation:** The marketer's key strategic tool is information of customers and their dynamic definition of value. Intelligence generation includes not only the expression of customer needs but it also analysis of exogenous factors influencing needs and preferences such as competitive actions, government regulations and technological change. The starting point of a market orientation is market intelligence generation which refers to the collection and assessment of both customers' needs and preferences and other environmental forces.
- (b) **Intelligence Dissemination:** Competitive advantage increasingly lies in firm's ability to use market intelligence. Intelligence dissemination refers to the process of exchange of market orientation within a given organisation. Effective dissemination of market intelligence is important because it provides a proper knowledge of market to all the departments in the organisations and also because there is an inverse relationship between the degree of individualism and market intelligence dissemination. The higher the market intelligence dissemination, the lower will be the degree of individualism.
- (c) **Responsiveness to Intelligence:** Responsiveness is the action taken in reply to the stimulus that is generated and disseminated. It takes the form of selecting target a audience, planning and designing products and services. It helps in analysing and fulfilling the needs of current and prospective customers. Therefore, for higher market intelligence utilisation, the level of uncertainty must be lowered (Kohli, Jaworski, & Kumar, 1993).

The philosophy - marketing concept whose implementation called market orientation is still regarded as a novel concept when it comes to the public sector in developing economies like Ghana. Even though the market

orientation construct since, 1990 has attracted several interests from marketing scholars (Schalk, 2008; Pattanayak, Koilakuntla, & Punyatoya, 2017; Webb et al., 2000; Kholi and Jaworski, 1993) because of its

perceived positive relationship with business outcomes such as service quality (Chang & Chen, 1998; Samat,

Ramayah, & Mat Saad, 2006; Samat et al., 2006) customer satisfaction (Pattanayak, Koilakuntla, & Punyatoya,

2017; Webb et al., 2000; Kholi and Jaworski, 1993) and firm performance (Mahmoud et al., 2010; Hinson et al., 2008; Osuagwu, 2006; Kuada & Buatsi, 2005). The concept has still not received the needed attention it deserves

when it comes to the public sector as compared to the private sector in the developing context and more especially the sub Saharan Africa. This widespread studies in the private sector in developed countries as well as in developing countries (Mahmoud, 2011; Mahmoud et al., 2010; Hinson et al., 2008; Dwairi et al., 2007; Osuagwu, 2006; Kuada & Buatsi, 2005; Appiah-Adu & Ranchhod, 1998; Jaworski & Kohli, 1993; Rucket, 1992) have mostly found a positive relationship with business performance. Developments in the economy such as privatization of public organization, commercialization and competitive tendering have put pressure on public organizations to provide services that meet the requirements of the citizenry (Day et al., 1998 cited in Mahmoud and Hinson, 2012). Hence, public sector organizations are forced to prioritise the needs of their customers in their strategic planning process. Private sector firms make use of market orientation to achieve higher performance or productivity by creating sustainable competitive advantage (Aaker, 1989) through effective and efficient creation of better service for its customers (Kholi and Jaworski, 1990). Market orientation is therefore one of the tools that public sector firms can make use of in order to achieve the same benefits that private sector firms are enjoying. Several studies on market orientation since 1990's have focused on the private sector especially in businesses whose core objective is profit and shareholder welfare maximisation (e.g Mahmoud, 2011; Mahmoud et al., 2010; Hinson et al., 2008; Bennet, 2005). Nevertheless, the few studies on the public sector (e.g Cervera et al., 2001) seem to have been founded solely on the conceptualisation of Kholi and Jaworski (1990). There has not been many works developed from the Narver and Slater's, (1990) conceptualization of market orientation even though the literature has indicated that both views of market orientation concept overlap. From a developing economy perspective, this study attempts to contribute to the market orientation literature by focusing on the public sector using the Narver and Slater's (1990) conceptualization since it has received little attention in the sub Saharan Africa in the field of public sector and more importantly the utility services sector from developing country context and also assessing market orientation from the perspective of customers which

has been a subject of recommendation for most scholars who conducted studies on market orientation.

The paper first introduced the topic under discussion. The second and third section discusses literature and The paper first introduced the topic under discussion. The second and third section discusses literature and the conceptual framework of the study and theoretical background and hypotheses development respectively. The fourth section addresses the methodology and whilst the fifth and sixth discusses the findings of the study and presents the conclusions on the paper. The seventh and the last section presents the limitations and future research directions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Market Orientation

Marketing works to actualize potential exchanges for the purpose of satisfying human needs and wants and emerged as the management function after using various advanced technique. Customers have a wider choice, so innovative and aggressive marketing strategies are required to retain and increase profitable share in market. Marketing has become necessary for setting up of target market, identifying the present and future needs of market for servicing customers.

The development of market orientation and competitiveness becomes a part of organisations in different economies. The competitiveness is measured through the multi-dimensional concept of organisational adaptability. Three main points which clarifies the meaning of competitiveness are adaptability to changes in the business environment, advantages across marketing mix and performance (Akimova, 2000).

Increase in the environmental uncertainties would influence the market orientation and performance relationship. It acts as a moderator in relationship between market orientation and organisational performance in the organisation. Those organisations that are following the concept of market orientation have seen positive impact on their performance irrespective of the degree of environmental uncertainty (Lonial & Raju, 2001).

Market orientation has deep and strong impact on the performance of the firm. Cost based and revenue-based performance is measured more in manufacturing organisations than in service organisations. This is because there is higher level of customization in service organisations than in manufacturing organisations (Kirca, Jayachandra, & Bearden, 2005).

Market orientation has been considered the most important aspect for service companies because it gives customer's information. It helps in determining the existing and potential customers (Favalgi, 2006).

Organizational culture includes customer care as its key and it also involves the efforts to understand the needs of customers through market orientation. So, if service sector organisations follow market orientation, then it would lead to improved service quality. It enables the organisation to provide quality services to their customers in order to satisfy needs of their customers (Chakrabarty, 2007).

Market orientation focuses on customers and help to maintain the relationship between the sellers and buyers in order to enhance customer satisfaction, customer loyalty in order to create value for business (Liyun, 2008).

2.2 Service Quality

Service quality leads to service loyalty. It is important for each organisation to understand the needs and wants of their customers. This is possible through market orientation and then organisation can use that information to

provide quality service to their customers. By providing quality service, organisation can satisfy the customers which enhance customer loyalty. These strategies will allow the firm to reduce the defections and improve their performance. So, by getting better service quality firm can implement market orientation more contentedly. (Caruana, 2002)

Purohit H.C and Avinash D. Pathardikar, in their research paper said that the perceptions of the customers on different banks vary due to the behaviour of the individual employees or officers. The five dimensions of SERVQUAL were observed as ideal in all the banks apart from the reliability of the employees (Purohit & Pathardikar, 2007).

Ashok Kumar and Rajesh had found in their study that both public sector banks and private sector banks lack one or the other aspect of service quality and there is no major difference between overall customer satisfactions in the banks. The paper concludes that banks should aims at satisfying the customers by providing maximum features in their banking services and products. Technological up gradation and development of techno-savvy products should be carried out for effective implementation of service quality (Kumar & R, 2009).

Gayathri Balakrishnan R, said that change is the only constant thing in life. In the present changed environment and life styles of customers, it can easily be encashed by the banks by providing good quality services at the right time and at the right place. The bankers should give attention to customers' perceptions and the expectations. The researcher concluded that the bank requires providing high touch services rather than high tech services (Balakrishnan, 2010).

Sunny Bose and Nitin Gupta (2013) studied the difference in service quality between public sector banks and new generation private sector banks in India based on SERVQUAL scale. The result shows that the new generation private banks give better service quality when compared to the public sector banks (Bose & Gupta, 2013).

To conclude, it can be traced that the importance of market orientation is increasing for organisations due to increasing competition in market. Marketers are trying to attract more and more customers by collecting information about the needs and preferences of the customers.

Literature review does not provide clear picture of Indian Banking Sector with respect to market orientation. So, it is clear through review of literature that researchers have identified the importance of market orientation. But as far as Indian Banking Industry is concerned, it is still untouched. Very few studies have tried to find out that how Indian Industry is using the concept of market orientation to enhance its performance. So, the impact of implementation of market orientation on the performance of Indian banking sector is also an area to explore.

3.0 Theoretical Background, Objectives and Hypotheses Development

3.1 Market Orientation and Service Quality

Market orientation has been outlined by various researchers. They have discussed the development of concept with respect to performance and its impact on different sectors. Market orientation is positioned as marketing's contribution to business strategy (Hunt & Lambe, 2000) and is measured as significant strategic orientation. Researchers emphasized that market orientation and other orientations come at a cost. For this reason, it is crucial to assess the bottom-line consequences of firm's market orientation. Several conceptual models have been developed to define the service quality construct and the factors in order to define consumer perceptions

and expectations. Service quality in banking is different from any other product/service environment. (Finn, 2004)

Service quality is an approach to manage business processes in order to ensure full satisfaction of the customers which will help to increase competitiveness and effectiveness of the industry. Quality in service is very important especially for the growth and development of service sector business enterprises (Powell, 1995). It works as an antecedent of customer satisfaction. With the increase of the importance of service sector in the economy of India, the measurement of service quality became important. (Dabholkar, 1996)

3.2 Objectives of the Study:

1. To investigate the relationship between market- orientation and service quality in banks.
2. To identify the factors of market- orientation that has dominant impact on service quality.

3.3 Hypothesis:

To fulfill above objectives, following hypotheses are formulated for understanding the relationship between market orientation and performance of banks:

- H1- There is significant relationship between market orientation and service quality.
- H2- There is significant relationship between intelligence generation and service quality.
- H3- There is significant relationship between intelligence dissemination and service quality.
- H4- There is significant relationship between responsiveness and service quality.

4.0 Methodology

Quantitative approach and exploratory design to research was adopted to ensure the generalization of the result and due to the fact that the study tries to determine the associations and causality among constructs in the framework as stated as a prerequisite to adopting the quantitative approach by (Stromgren, 2007) and exploratory because the study seeks new insights into market orientation (Robson, 2002). The proposed research format is based on cause-effect relationship between independent and dependent factors. The questionnaire method was used for data collection. All selected respondents received a survey questionnaire as part of data collection process. It is a form containing a series of questions to be asked to respondents. Structured questionnaire containing easily understandable questions were prepared. The starting point for development of the questionnaire was to create an initial version, that to be used for testing. The questionnaire's accuracy and reliability were checked with pilot test before finalization which has also included the testing of reliability of scales used and the validity of the questions.

The instrument to measure market orientation variables uses MARKOR (Kohli and Jaworski, 1990). On the other hand, service quality variable is measured by the two variables uses Likert Scale with 1-5 intervals.

In second section, respondents were asked about their expectation on various service dimensions (SERVQUAL) about retail banking. The third section survey customer level of perception towards various banking dimensions. Satisfaction towards tangibles, employee empathy, system assurance, responsiveness and reliability were measures in Likert scale.

The total number of respondents contacted was 250, but due to incomplete responses and other faults the final responses subjected to data analysis are 200. The high response rate of 80 percent was the effect of the constant

direct contact and reminders between respondents and researcher. The banks selected for the research were SBI & Bank of Baroda in Public Sector and HDFC & AXIS Bank in Private Sector.

5. Presentation and discussion of findings

5.1 Reliability Assessment

Achieving construct reliability is deemed as a necessary condition for any good quantitative analysis. The reliability of the developed questionnaire was tested by deploying the statistical test ‘Cronbach’s alpha’ to the responses received from 25 respondents selected randomly. The Cronbach’s alpha covering the overall responses should exceeded the reliability estimates (≥ 0.70) recommended by Nunnally (1967), which is considered a good sign of reliability of the questionnaire.

Table 5.1: Scale Reliability Statistics

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	200	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	200	100.0
a. List wise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha		N of Items	
.851		44	
Item-Total Statistics			

Relationship between Market Orientation and service Quality

Following Hypothesis are formulated to test the relation between dimensions of Market Orientation and Service Quality.

- H1- There is significant relationship between Market Orientation and Service Quality.
- H2- There is significant relationship between Intelligence Generation and Service Quality.
- H3- There is significant relationship between Intelligence Dissemination and Service Quality.
- H4- There is significant relationship between Responsiveness and Service Quality.

To test the above hypothesis, Pearson Bivariate correlation is applied. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) can have the values from +1 to -1. Value of $r=0$ indicates that there is no association/correlation between the two variables. Value >0 indicates a positive association.

Table 5.2: Correlation Analysis- Market orientation and Service Quality

Correlations			
		SQ	MO
SQ	Pearson Correlation	1	.778**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
MO	Pearson Correlation	.778**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

From the above table it can be concluded that there is a significant and positive relation between Market orientation and service quality. Hence, we can accept the hypothesis and conclude that bank market orientation practice like intelligence generation, intelligence dissemination and responsiveness influence service quality provided to customers.

Table 5.3: Correlation Analysis- Intelligence Generation and Service Quality

Correlations			
		SQ	InfGen
SQ	Pearson Correlation	1	.782**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
InfGen	Pearson Correlation	.782**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

From the above table it can be concluded that there is a significant and positive relation between intelligence generation and service quality. Hence, we can accept the hypothesis and conclude that bank

intelligence generation practice like discussing customers need at least once a year, finding out what products or services they will need in the future, conducting poll of customers to assess the quality of services, systematically collect information on competitor's strategies, periodically review changes in our business environment influence bank service quality provided to customers.

Table 5.4: Correlation Analysis- Intelligence Dissemination and Service Quality

Correlations			
		SQ	IntDiss
SQ	Pearson Correlation	1	.536**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
IntDiss	Pearson Correlation	.536**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the above table it can be concluded that there is a significant and positive relation between intelligence generation and service quality. Hence, we can accept the hypothesis and conclude that bank intelligence dissemination practice like discussing customer's future needs by marketing and other functional departments, collecting and dissemination of data customer satisfaction to all levels on a regular basis and reacting promptly on major changes in market influence service quality provided to customers.

Table 5.5: Correlation Analysis- Responsiveness and Service Quality

Correlations			
		SQ	InfResp
SQ	Pearson Correlation	1	.752**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
InfResp	Pearson Correlation	.752**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

	N	60	60
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

From the above table it can be concluded that there is a significant and positive relation between intelligence generation and service quality. Hence, we can accept the hypothesis and conclude that bank responsiveness practice like periodic review of product development efforts, plan suitable response to any changes in business environment, coordination among different departments, timely solution to customer complaints, prompt response to competitor strategy and responsive nature of bank employees influences service quality provided to customers.

6. Conclusion:

It is concluded that there is a significant and positive relation between Market orientation and service quality. Hence, we can accept the hypothesis and conclude that bank market orientation practice like intelligence generation, intelligence dissemination and responsiveness influence service quality provided to customers. In order to improve performance and quality of services, banks have to focus on market orientation. Market orientation is an organisational culture dedicated to deliver superior value to the customers. It is a value exchange process. A market-oriented culture is involved in providing the best services to their customers and also helps in knowing the current and anticipated needs of their customers. Furthermore, it is investigated that how market orientation is helpful in enhancing and improving the firm performance.

7. Limitations and Scope for further Research

There are some limitations associated with this study that need to be discussed. Firstly, the results obtained from this study cannot be generalised to a wide range of similar situations concerning banks because of the non-probability sampling technique used even though the methodology used in this study could be applied to these similar situations. Also, the issue of consumers' perceptions could be questioned because the sample size consisted of respondents that come from both public and private service providers that may differ. Carrying out this study on banks of different sizes could be a limitation because consumers could expect more from bigger banks than smaller ones.

A similar study could be conducted with a larger sample size so that results could be generalised to a larger population. This study can be carried out in other areas comprised of multiple cultures in order to find out the applicability of the SERVQUAL model in banks.

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